

TRANSPORT PROPERTIES OF DISORDERED
COMPOSITE MATERIALS FROM THE MICROSTRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

A series representation of a general n -point distribution function H_n that characterizes the microstructure of multiphase media is derived. This series expression enables one to systematically compute H_n for a certain class of models. It is shown that any of the statistical correlation functions which have arisen in expressions for the effective thermal conductivity σ_e of composite media and the fluid permeability k of porous media can be obtained from this single expression for H_n . This is followed by a description of a new highly accurate expression for the conductivity of dispersions of inclusions. Calculation of a rigorous bound on the permeability of a bed of spheres, which depends upon statistical information involving the particle-void interface, is presented.

INTRODUCTION

The determination of transport properties of porous and other composite media is of importance in a host of problems. For example, the geothermal temperature gradient depends upon the effective thermal conductivity σ_e of the fluid-saturated rock involved. A key parameter in the study of convection in a porous medium is the fluid permeability k . The design of thermally insulating materials, such as fiber-ceramic composite materials used on advanced re-entry vehicles and high-performance insulation for buildings and cold storage, depends upon the heat transfer and flow characteristics of the heterogeneous materials.

In order to exactly predict the effective transport property of random multiphase media, an infinite set of correlation functions, which statistically characterize the microstructure, must be known [1,2]. Except in a few special cases, the infinite set of correlation functions is never known and hence an exact calculation of the bulk property is generally out of the question. Rigorous bounding methods provide a means of estimating the effective property given a limited amount of microstructural information on the heterogeneous material. Rigorous bounds are useful because: (i) they enable one to test the merits of a theory, (ii) one of the bounds can typically provide a relatively

accurate estimate of the property, and (iii) as successively more microstructural information is included, the bounds become progressively tighter. Here we shall study and evaluate bounds on the effective thermal conductivity σ_e of composites and on the fluid permeability k of porous media that depend upon the details of the microstructure through various sets of statistical correlation functions.

The two-phase conductivity bounds of Beran [3] depend upon the correlation functions $S_1(x_1)$, $S_2(x_1, x_2)$, and $S_3(x_1, x_2, x_3)$. The $S_n(x^n)$ ($x^n \equiv x_1, \dots, x_n$) give the probability of finding n points at positions x^n , respectively, all in one of the two phases, say phase 1. (For statistically homogeneous media, S_1 is simply equal to ϕ_1 , the volume fraction of phase 1.) Milton [4] has formally derived general bounds on σ_e that depend upon the set S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n , for arbitrary n . Torquato [5] has recently obtained bounds on σ_e for systems composed of spheres of variable penetrability distributed throughout a matrix. These bounds depend upon a different set of correlation functions, namely, G_0, G_1, \dots, G_n . $G_n(x; r^n)$ characterizes the correlation associated with finding a point at x in the matrix (or void) phase and a configuration of spheres with centers at r^n . The permeability bounds of Weissberg and Prager [6] and of Doi [7] depend upon, among other quantities, certain two-point correlation functions that involve information about the two-phase interface.

Historically, practical application of all but one of the bounds described above (i.e., the bounds due to Torquato [5]) has been very limited because of the difficulty involved in obtaining even lower-order correlation functions either theoretically or experimentally. Recent advances in the characterization of the microstructure of random media suggests that this impasse is in the process of being overcome. For a statistically inhomogeneous two-phase medium consisting of identical particles dispersed throughout a matrix or void phase (phase 1) such that the location of each inclusion is fully specified by a position vector (e.g., spheres, disks, and oriented cubes, squares, and ellipsoids), the S_n can be systematically represented as an infinite series [8]. This series representation of the S_n has led to the evaluation of lower-order S_n (i.e., S_1, S_2 , and S_3) [9-12] and hence of conductivity bounds [13-15] for nontrivial models of composite and porous media. Recently, a highly accurate expression for σ_e of dispersions, which depends upon S_1, S_2 , and S_3 was derived [2]. Using series representations of the G_n , the conductivity bounds due to Torquato [5] have also been evaluated for various models [5,16].

There has been comparatively much less progress in the calculation of permeability bounds. Bounds on k computed to date are only useful for very high porosities [6,17]. A stumbling block in the evaluation of such bounds has been a lack of a systematic means of computing the correlation functions that arise here, i.e., quantities involving two-phase interface information.

We have recently [18] derived a series expression for a very general n -point distribution function H_n , for inhomogeneous media composed of particles distributed throughout matrix or void. Using this single expression for H_n , we may now derive and compute any of the various sets of correlation functions that have been described in the literature, i.e., S_n, G_n , and the surface correlation functions, for a wide class of models of isotropic, anisotropic, and inhomogeneous media. The subsequent section describes this general formalism. Conductivity and permeability expressions which depend upon the H_n are then discussed.

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE MICROSTRUCTURE

For simplicity, we shall consider the model of spheres or parallel circular cylinders (circular disks in two dimensions) distributed throughout matrix or void. The solvent particles are in general distributed with arbitrary degree of impenetrability. The degree of impenetrability is characterized by some parameter λ whose value varies between zero (in the case where the spheres are randomly centered and thus completely uncorrelated, i.e., "fully penetrable spheres") and unity (in the instance of totally impenetrable spheres). An example of a distribution involving intermediate values of λ is the penetrable-concentric-shell (PCS) model [19]. In the PCS model (depicted in Fig. 1) spheres (disks) of radius R are statistically distributed throughout space subject only to the condition of a mutually impenetrable core of radius λR , $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$. Such a model enables one to study the effect of the degree of connectivity on the effective transport property. The degree of the connectivity of the individual phases may greatly influence the transport properties of disordered multiphase media, particularly when the phase properties differ significantly. For example, the PCS model may serve as a useful model for consolidated media, such as sandstones and other rocks, and sintered materials.

FIG. 1. A computer-generated realization of a distribution of disks of radius $R = \sigma/2$ (shaded region) in a matrix (unshaded region) in the PCS model [19]. The disks have an impenetrable core of diameter $\lambda\sigma$ indicated by the smaller, black circular region. Here $\lambda = 0.5$ and the particle volume fraction is 0.3.

The general n -point distribution function $H_n(\underline{x}^m; \underline{x}^{p-m}; \underline{r}^q)$ gives the correlation associated with finding: m points at \underline{x}^m on certain surfaces within the system, $p - m$ points at \underline{x}^{p-m} ($\Xi \underline{x}_{m+1} \dots \underline{x}_p$) in certain portions of the matrix (or void) phase, and the centroids of the particles at \underline{r}^q , where $n = p + q$. From this single function one can obtain all of the various sets of correlation functions described in the Introduction. For example, in a special limit, the n -point matrix probability function $S_n(\underline{x}^n) = H_n(\emptyset; \underline{x}^n; \emptyset)$ and $G_q(\underline{x}_1; \underline{r}^q) = H_n(\emptyset; \underline{x}_1; \underline{r}^q)$, where \emptyset denotes the null set. Similarly, in this limit $H_2(\underline{x}_1; \underline{x}_2; \emptyset)$ and $H_2(\underline{x}_1, \underline{x}_2; \emptyset; \emptyset)$ are the surface-matrix and surface-surface correlation functions defined by Doi [7], and $H_2(\underline{x}_1; \emptyset; \underline{r}_1)$ is a two-point surface correlation function closely related to the one defined by Weissberg and Prager [6].

It can be shown that [18]

$$H_n(\underline{x}^m; \underline{x}^{p-m}; \underline{r}^q) = \sum_{s=0}^{\infty} (-1)^s H_n^{(s)}(\underline{x}^m; \underline{x}^{p-m}; \underline{r}^q), \quad n=p+q, \quad (1)$$

where

$$H_n^{(s)}(\underline{x}^m; \underline{x}^{p-m}; \underline{r}^q) = (-1)^m \frac{\partial}{\partial a_1} \dots \frac{\partial}{\partial a_m} G_n^{(s)}(\underline{x}^p; \underline{r}^q), \quad (2)$$

$$G_n^{(s)}(\underline{x}^p; \underline{r}^q) = \prod_{\ell=1}^q \prod_{k=1}^p e(y_{k\ell}; a_k) \quad (3)$$

$$\times \int \rho_{q+s}(\underline{r}^{q+s}) \prod_{j=q+1}^{q+s} m^{(p)}(\underline{x}^p; \underline{r}_j) d\underline{r}_j,$$

Here ρ_n is the n -particle probability density that characterizes the configuration of n spheres with positions \underline{r}^q and $y_{ij} = |\underline{x}_i - \underline{r}_j|$. The quantity $m^{(p)}$ involves a product of step functions [18]. Given ρ_n for the ensemble, we may now compute H_n from Eqs. (1)-(3).

CONDUCTIVITY AND PERMEABILITY EXPRESSIONS

Here we shall discuss some recent progress made in the evaluation of conductivity and permeability bounds which incorporate some of the statistical quantities described in the previous section.

Recently, Torquato [2] has derived, from a rigorous lower bound on σ_e , an expression for the effective conductivity σ_e of a dispersion:

$$\frac{\sigma_e}{\sigma_1} = \frac{1 + 2\phi_2\beta - 2\phi_1\zeta_2\beta^2}{1 - \phi_2\beta - 2\phi_1\zeta_2\beta^2} \quad (4)$$

Here ϕ_i is the volume fraction of the i th phase, ζ_2 is an integral that depends upon the three-point probability function S_3 [8], and β is a parameter that depends in a simple manner upon the σ_1 .

To test relation (4) we have compared (in Fig. 2) predicted values of σ_e/σ_1 obtained from it for periodic lattices of spheres (using the tabulation of ζ_2 for such system obtained by McPhedran and Milton [20]) to exact numerical results of σ_e/σ_1 [21,22]. The agreement with exact results is found to be excellent for a wide range of $\alpha = \sigma_2/\sigma_1$ and sphere volume fraction ϕ_2 .

We have also compared predicted values of σ_e/σ_1 obtained from Eq. (4) for random distributions of impenetrable spheres (using the results of Torquato and Lado [15]) to Turner's measurements of the electrical conductivity of a fluidized bed of impenetrable spheres [23]. Fig. 3 gives such a comparison for the extreme case $\alpha = \infty$. The agreement here is not as good as in the case of cubic lattices of spheres. This is due primarily to the fact that at moderate to high densities, a fluidized bed is probably not accurately modelled by an equilibrium dispersion of spheres. However, for the wide range of phase conductivities and volume fractions reported in Ref. 23, Turner's data are the best available measurements for the conductivity of equi-sized spheres. Note that as α is made smaller the agreement between Eq. (4) and Turner's data improves.

FIG. 2. Comparison of Eq. (4) for σ_e/σ_1 (solid lines) to exact numerical results for simple, body-centered, and face-centered cubic lattices (O, Δ , \square , respectively) [21,22], as a function of ϕ_2 . Here $\alpha = \infty$.

FIG. 3. Comparison of Eq. (4) for σ_e/σ_1 (solid line) to Turner's data [23] for a random distribution of spheres (filled circles), as a function of ϕ_2 . Here $\alpha = \infty$.

Using the results for the general n -point distribution function H_n described in the previous section [18], Torquato [24] has computed the surface-matrix and surface-surface correlation functions; key quantities which arise in the Doi bound on the fluid permeability [7]. Recently, Torquato [18] used these results to evaluate the Doi lower bound on the inverse permeability k^{-1} for a bed of hard spheres. Fig. 4 compares these results to the well-known Kozeny-Carman empirical relation. This is the first time that rigorous bounds have been shown to yield results for the permeability which are relatively accurate over the entire range of porosities.

FIG. 4. Doi's lower bound on k_s/k for a bed of impenetrable spheres compared to the empirical Kozeny-Carman relation. Here k_s is the Stokes-law-dilute-limit permeability.

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